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Research Article

INSOMNIA IN ADOLESCENTS, ITS ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL FACTORS IN RIYADH DURING 2014 - 2015

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Abstract:

Almost everyone experiences some form of short-term insomnia in his or her life. Insomnia occurs in one-third of the general population (Einass Al-Eisa, 2013)

Teens have a harder time falling asleep. Sometimes this delay in the sleep-wake cycle is so severe that it affects a person's daily activities.

Insomnia is a sleep disorder that is characterized by difficulty falling asleep, is a literal meaning of total lack of sleep, in clinical and practical terms insomnia has come to refer to a difficulty in initiating and/or maintaining sleep, or non-restorative, non-refreshing sleep. Insomnia is traditionally viewed and treated as a symptom rather than a disease. It is difficult to define what normal sleep is because everyone is different. Your age, lifestyle, environment and diet all play a part in influencing the amount of sleep you need. Women are more likely to experience insomnia than men and it is affect all age groups.

Adequate sleep for adolescents is extremely important for their biological and psychological health, short sleep duration will lead to negative effects on adolescent daily life.

Research shows that teens need at least 8½ hours of sleep a night. (Rupal Christine Gupta, MD) Studies have found that many teens have trouble falling asleep.(Rupal Christine Gupta, MD) .

Students who report insomnia, inadequate sleep, irregular sleep patterns and or poor sleep quality do not perform as well in school as others (James F. Pagel).

Better school performance is associated with more time in bed, better sleep quality, fewer nighttimes, less napping and less difference between weekday and weekend sleep times.

Most studies have focused on management of clinical insomnia among the middle- aged and elderly, In this research we will See how social and electronic and others factors will impact on insomnia in high secondary schools.

in order to know more about insomnia we designed flowing questions:

What relationship between insomnia and academic achievements?

What relationship of insomnia and use of electronics?

How the insomnia effective in body weight?

What factors increasing insomnia?

What actions taken by those with insomnia?

Problems which might have in this research are small sample size, ambiguity of insomnia definition, the cross sectional design and possible technical obstacles such as how to approach the students.

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INTRODUCTION:

ABDULGHANI, 2012. A high prevalence of sleep disorder was found in this group of students, specifically female students. Analysis of the relationship between sleep disorder and academic performance indicates a significant relationship between abnormal Epworth sleepiness scale (ESS) scores, total sleeping hours, and academic performance.

Bernert, Rebecca A.; Merrill, Katherine A.; Braithwaite, Scott R.; Van Orden, Kimberly A.; Joiner Jr., Thomas E. The present study prospectively investigated the association between family life stress and insomnia symptoms among 115 undergraduates, ages 17-22 years. Regression analyses were conducted to test study predictions. Family life stress was significantly associated with increased insomnia symptomatology. Results also revealed that negative family life events, together with academic stress, predicted the highest levels of insomnia.

Brunborg GS, Mentzoni RA, Molde H. 20th of Dec 2011, Department of Psychosocial Science, University of Bergen, Norway. 2011 European Sleep Research Society. Study investigated the use of media in the bedroom and its relationships with sleep habits and symptoms of insomnia. The results of our study suggest that the use of computers and mobile telephones in the bedroom, may be associated with poor sleep habits among young adults, but not with symptoms of insomnia.

Denise Mann | March 25, 2009. University of Chicago. Source: Mark Mahowald, MD, director, Minnesota Regional Sleep Disorders Center, Hennepin County. Insomnia is a prevalent health complaint that is often difficult to evaluate reliably. There is evidence that sleep loss is linked to weight gain, in particular abdominal weight gain. Too little sleep has been shown to slow the body's resting metabolism.

Einass Al-Eisa,1 Syamala Buragadda,2,* Ganeswara Rao Melam,2 Atheer O. Al-Osaimi,2 Huda A. Al-Mubarak,2 and Noura A. Al-Huwaime. Ther Sci. 2013 Nov; 25 NCB, Saudi Arabia. Association between Physical Activity and Insomnia among Saudi Female College Students; The results show that physical activity increased from the first to the third week. Association between insomnia and sleep problems Physical activity measured as the number of steps taken correlated with the ISI values showing a moderately negative correlation.

Haazzaa M. Al-Hazzaa . A cross-sectional study from three major cities in Saudi Arabia 2012 July – September. Riyadh, SAUDI ARABIA. Prevalence of short sleep duration and its association with obesity among adolescents 15- to 19-year olds. The mean (SD) of sleep duration was 7.2 (1.6) hours/day with no significant differences between males and females. About 31% of the participants obtain less than 7 hours of sleep per day, while approximately 50% of the sample gets less than 8 hours of daily sleep.

In Conclusion, the present study observed a high prevalence of short sleep duration among Saudi adolescents 15- to 19-year olds, associated with increased risk of overweight and obesity.

Hamza M. Abdulghani, in Kingdom of Saudi Arabia at King Saud University in 2012 found a high prevalence of sleep disorder was found in this group of students, specifically female students. Analysis of the relationship between sleep disorder and academic performance indicates a significant relationship between abnormal ESS scores, total sleeping hours, and academic performance.

H.M. Al-hazzaa, A.O. Mussaiger, N.A. Abahussain in 22nd of March 2013. Collage of education; king saud university, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. Titled **examine association of insomnia to environmental and social factor.** Life style correlate of self reported sleep duration among Saudi adolescents. Lifestyle factor are important deterrents of adequate sleep among

adolescent. Short duration of sleep among Saudi adolescents (< 8h/day) 15 -19 years was associated with several lifestyle factors. Intervention programs aiming for improving sleeping habits among adolescents need to consider such potential association of lifestyle variables with sleep duration.

Harvey, Allison G. The aim of this article is to review progress toward developing a cognitive theory of and therapy for chronic insomnia. The current treatment of choice, which devotes approximately one session to cognitive therapy. This treatment is derived from a cognitive model that specifies five processes that function to maintain insomnia.

James F, Wednesday, May 14, 2008. American Academy of Sleep Medicine. Insomnia complaints among college students are significantly associated with a decline in school performance based on self reported grade point average (GPA). According to the results, 69.7 percent of those students with low GPAs had difficulty falling asleep, and 72.7 percent had difficulty concentrating during the day. In conclusion, Insomnia is a classification of sleep disorders in which a person has trouble falling asleep, staying asleep or waking up too early. It is the most commonly reported sleep disorder.

Jill Baxter, March 2013, United States. Scientists study link between insomnia and electronic devices. According to National Public Radio (NPR), 60 million Americans suffer from insomnia. With the sale and use of electronic devices such as e-readers and other tablets on the rise, scientists are looking into the possible connection between the use of electronic devices before going to sleep and insomnia. Artificial light causes the body to be alert and more awake by stimulating the brain. According to a study conducted in 2003 by Belgian researchers, 2.2 percent of teenagers were woken up every night by a text message. Mobile phones were not as prevalent in 2003, and with nearly 85 percent of teenagers now carrying phones around on a daily basis, researchers have concluded that more and more teenagers are being woken up daily by the ringing of their cell phones.

John M. Grohol, Psy.D. on March 30, 2009. University of California, Los Angeles, health science. In the study, researchers compared healthy sleepers with those suffering from chronic insomnia and measured the levels of the two hormones at various times throughout the night. The current study shows

that insomnia patients have a dysregulation in energy balance that could explain why these patients gain weight over time. For the study, 38 male participants were divided into two groups, 14 insomnia sufferers and 24 healthy subjects. Both groups had similar ages and body weight.

In conclusion, this is an exciting finding because it highlights how diverse behaviors like sleep and eating are connected. We are just beginning to explore the possible consequences of these connections.

J. Moo Estrella, Rosado Narvaez, Valencia Flores, Yanez oría. 28 September to 2 October 2013, Valencia, Spain. The objective of this study was to determine whether or not differences in physical activity in groups with different forms of insomnia existed. The 33% of the total sample had insomnia, within this group, 53% had insomnia for inadequate sleep hygiene, 52% had psychological insomnia.

In conclusion, Results show that physical activity is reduced only in the group with psychological insomnia; this group spends more time sitting and less time walking and exercising.

Mak KK1. In 2007-2008 in Hong Kong poorer academic performance was associated with sleep debt, and symptoms of insomnia and OSA. Sleep compensation but not naps may be a protective factor of poor academic performance.

Michael J. Breus, September 2007, United States. Assess relationship of insomnia and use of electronics. It should come as no surprise that staring at a computer screen and enthusiastically typing or surfing not only can steal precious time you should be banking in deep sleep, but the actual light emanating from the screen can also disrupt your body's ability to prepare for sleep and down. Numerous survey findings have shown that people who spend more pre-bedtime hours using the Internet or watching television are more likely to report that they don't get enough sleep. In a study written up in the industry journal *Sleep and Biological Rhythms* just last month, researchers confirmed this finding and took it a step further by saying that longer electronic media use before sleep triggers a self-perception of insufficient sleep.

Pasquale K. Alvaro, Rachel M. Roberts, Jodie K. Harris. May 20, 2014. To investigate the independent effects of depression and subtypes of anxiety on insomnia. In all, 318 South Australian high school students from grades 7–11 (age range, 12–18

years; mean, 14.97 ± 1.34) participated in this cross-sectional study. Validated self-report questionnaires were used to assess insomnia, depression, subtypes of anxiety, and chronotype.

In Conclusions, Insomnia independently predicts depression and is predicted by depression, but not by other forms of anxiety. The independent prediction of insomnia on PD is unlikely to be clinically significant.

Roach A.Merdad , Leena A.Merdad , Rawan A.Nassif in 9th of June 2014.Collage of medicine , king abdulaziz university ,Jeddah .Titled examine association of insomnia to environmental and social factor. Research investigating the prevalence of cause of adolescent sleep problem, focused in three aspects: -Sleep duration, sleep quality and daytime sleepiness. Sleep factors of adolescent are affected by social, psychological , physiological and environment factors . Adolescent in Saudi Arabia showed high percentage of poor sleep quality compared to adolescent of other countries.

Talebian A, Soltani B, Haji Rezaei M. Referred to a Neurology Clinic in Kashan, Iran.Department of Pediatrics, Kashan University of Medical Sciences, Kashan, Iran.One hundred fourteen children (44 male and 70 female) with headaches were enrolled in the study. The types of headaches were comprised as follows: 67 cases of migraines, 38 cases of tension-type headaches, 2 cases of cluster headaches, and 7 cases of secondary headaches. Pulsating headaches, family history of headaches, insomnia, and pain severity had higher prevalence in migraines patients. Physicians should extend their information gathering about primary and secondary headaches. Sleep disturbances and a family history of headaches were the most important factors associated with migraine headaches.

Voinescu ,Szentagotai-Tatar, J Mol Psychiatry .2015 Jan 31.Sleep hygiene awareness was moderate on the whole and significantly worse in young adults and in those complaining of poor sleep. Sleep quality was average and linked positively with diurnal preference .Our results suggest that better sleep hygiene awareness does not necessarily guarantee better sleep quality and that it may actually be an indicator of dissatisfaction with the obtained sleep.

A. Approach:

Methodology

Group B

April 2015

Study Design: a descriptive observational cross sectional study

Study Area: at 3 different high schools in Riyadh city

Study Population: consists of adolescent students of female gender

Study Sample: study sample of this population who met inclusion criteria

Sample Size: 200 students as random samples

Baseline demographic characteristics of the sample:

Age, Saudi or not, Married or not

Inclusion Criteria:

Have any type of Insomnia

Female gender

Age between 16 – 19 years

Girls study in the selected schools

Exclusion Criteria:

Girls who have Endocrine disorder

Male gender

Students older or younger than high school grades

Students using drugs causes Insomnia as side effect

Baseline demographic characteristics:

A. Data needs:

We will address Reliability and Validity of instruments/measures

Questionnaire Closed ended questions

Sort of variable	Variable	Type
Dependent variables	Insomnia	Acute or chronic
Independent variable	Age	In completed Ys.- continuous
	No. of adolescent	1,2,3 discrete
	Body weight	
	Watching TV	
	Electronic devices	In bed before sleep

	Dietary pattern	Frequency of meals/day
	Psychological problems	panic, phobia, OCD and posttraumatic stress
	Community	
	Education	

Cleveland Adolescent Sleepiness Questionnaire

We want to collect information to conduct a research about insomnia. your participation will help us in the research. the data collected is treated with privacy and high confidentiality.

We would like to know about when you might feel sleepy during a usual week. For each statement, mark the circle of the response that best fits with how often it applies to you. It's important to answer them by yourself.

What is your age? _____ **What grade are you in?** _____

What is your marital status?

- A. single
- B. married
- C. divorced
- D. widowed

In general, would you say your health is:

- Excellent
- Good
- Fair
- Poor

How many nights out of 7 in a typical week do you have problems falling asleep?

- 1-2
- 3-5
- 6-7

How many meals do you eat during the day?

- 1-3
- More than three meals

Do you suffer from obesity?

- Yes
- No

Is there anything in your home that disrupts your sleep such as infant (s), noise, lights, partner snoring, TV, pets?

- A. Yes
- B. NO
- C. If your answer YES write the cause: _____

Do you have any family or social problems?

- Yes
- NO

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Most nights/days	Always
Do you have trouble falling asleep?					
Do you have trouble staying asleep?					
When you wake during the night do you have trouble getting back to sleep?					
Do you fall asleep during your morning classes?					
Do you feel sleepy when you do your homework in the evening after school?					
Do you take anything to help you sleep?					
Is there anything in your home that disrupts your sleep such as infant (s), noise, lights, partner snoring, TV, pets?					

Thanks for your cooperation

Data analysis:

After gathering the data, it will be cleared and then analyzed manually.

Then it will be presented in a dummy table.

Data will be presented as (dummy table):

Statistical test:

Ethical consideration:

Before conducting the study a written informed consent be taken from each participants.

Confidentiality of the data will be maintained.

A permission will be obtained from the college administration & the concerned schools.

The questionnaire will be anonymous

We conducted a self-administered questionnaire to 3 high school female students; total number of responders were -----.

Data at each center were checked and entered into a computer using standardized entry codes written on an

SPSS data file. The entered data were then sent to one central processing place (Riyadh). At the central processing center, all data were checked again for outliers and wrong entries. Data were then analyzed using SPSS.

The descriptive characteristics of the participants are shown in [Table 1].

Here fill your dummy tables according to your objectives:

Figure 1: Sleep duration (hours/day) relative to age. Two ways ANOVA results: P values for age = 0.002, gender = 0.897, and age by gender interaction = 0.386

Figure 3: Sleep duration (hours/day) relative to B Wt. cutoff categories (*significant difference between normal

weight and obese adolescents at P values = 0.002).

The main findings of this study indicate that depending on the cut-off values used, about -----% to -----% of Saudi adolescents do not obtain enough daily sleep, and that sleep duration decreases/or increases with increasing age from ----- to ----- years of age.

The average sleep duration (----- hours/day) found in our study appears lower than that reported by (----- from lit. reviews).

The reduced sleep duration observed among Saudi adolescents in this study may be attributed to several factors -----, -----, -----.

The mean (SD) of sleep duration was 7.2 (1.6) hours/day with no significant differences between

males and females. About 31% of the participants obtain less than 7 hours of sleep per day, while approximately 50% of the sample gets less than 8 hours of daily sleep. Two-way ANCOVA results while controlling for the effect of age revealed a significant gender by school-type interaction ($P < 0.001$). In addition, adequate sleep duration increased the odds of having normal weight (adjusted odds ratios = 1.28, 95% CI = 1.08-1.50, $P = 0.003$).

We went to two different school al rowad school and manarat al riyadh school on 3rd of November and the survey was answered by 200 girls

We went to two different school al rowad school and manarat al riyadh school on 3rd of November and the survey was answered by 200 girls.

Insomnia Results:

Table 1: Overall results.

Item	Mean(SD)	Categories	Participant n(%)	P-value
Age	16.62(0.70)	15	6(3.9)	
		16	58(37.9)	
		17	75(49)	
		18	11(7.2)	
		19	1(0.7)	
		Missing	2(1.3)	
Grade	11.48(0.50)	11	78(51)	<0.0001
		12	73(47.7)	
		Missing	2(1.3)	
Marital status	1.00(0.00)	Single	153(100)	
Health state	3.67(0.60)	Excellent	1(0.7)	0.02
		Vary good	8(5.2)	
		good	31(20.3)	
		poor	113(73.9)	
Nights of interrupted sleep/Week	1.36(0.55)	6 to 7	6(3.9)	0.77
		5 to 3	43(28.1)	
		2 to 1	103(67.3)	
		Missing	1(0.7)	

School performance	2.48(0.61)	Excellent	83(54.2)	0.31
		Very good	60(39.2)	
		good	10(6.5)	
Number of meals/Day	1.17(0.377)	1 to 3	127(83)	0.15
		more than 3	26(17)	
Do you have gross obesity	1.08(0.27)	Yes	140(91.5)	0.86
		No	12(7.8)	
Any factors at home interrupt your sleep	1.27(0.44)	Yes	109(71.2)	0.38
		No	42(27.5)	
Any family or social problems	1.13(0.33)	Yes	133(86.9)	0.96
		No	20(13.1)	
Does Internet related to your sleep pattern	1.82(0.38)	Yes	27(17.6)	0.99
		No	126(82.4)	
Do you have problem in going to bed	2.81(0.92)	Never	12(7.8)	0.001
		Rarely	43(28.1)	
		Sometimes	59(38.6)	
		Most nights	35(22.9)	
		Always	2(1.3)	
		Missing	2(1.3)	
Do you have problems continuing your sleep	3.06(4.31)	Never	32(20.9)	0.09
		Rarely	47(30.7)	
		Sometimes	36(23.5)	
		Most nights	22(14.4)	
		Always	14(9.2)	
		Missing	2(1.4)	

If you wake up at night, do you face problem go back to sleep	2.80(1.25)	Never	31(20.3)	0.2
		Rarely	26(17)	
		Sometimes	53(34.6)	
		Most nights	24(15.7)	
		Always	17(11.1)	
		Missing	2(1.3)	
Do you nap during morning classes	2.09(1.07)	Never	54(35.3)	0.14
		Rarely	53(34.6)	
		Sometimes	27(17.6)	
		Most nights	15(9.8)	
		Always	4(2.6)	
Do you feel sleepy when doing homework at evening	3.24(1.20)	Never	14(9.2)	0.02
		Rarely	26(17)	
		Sometimes	49(32)	
		Most nights	35(22.9)	
		Always	28(18.3)	
		Missing	1(0.7)	
Do you take something to help you to sleep	1.32(0.79)	Never	125(81.7)	0.77
		Rarely	12(7.8)	
		Sometimes	10(6.5)	
		Most nights	3(2)	
		Always	2(1.3)	
		Missing	1(0.7)	
Did you loose your interest in your usual	2.19(1.28)	Never	66(43.1)	0.9

hobbies and activities				
		Rarely	25(16.3)	
		Sometimes	37(24.2)	
		Most nights	11(7.2)	
		Always	12(7.8)	
		Missing	2(1.3)	
Do you take caffeine and/or energy drinks	2.75(1.50)	Never	48(31.4)	0.19
		Rarely	22(14.4)	
		Sometimes	33(21.6)	
		Most nights	20(13.1)	
		Always	30(19.6)	
Any health problems affect your sleep	1.41(0.86)	Never	116(75.8)	0.49
		Rarely	19(12.4)	
		Sometimes	11(7.2)	
		Most nights	5(3.3)	
		Always	2(1.3)	
How often do you use Internet or electronics games	4.56(0.84)	Never	3(2)	0.5
		Rarely	2(1.3)	
		Sometimes	11(7.2)	
		Most nights	26(17)	
		Always	110(71.9)	
		Missing	1(0.7)	

All the student 153(100) are single

Table 1: Age distribution.

Categories	Participant n(%)
15	6(3.9)
16	58(37.9)
17	75(49)
18	11(7.2)
19	1(0.7)
Missing	2(1.3)

Most of participants were between 16-17 Years-old 133 (86.9%) Around half of student 78(51) are in grade 11 and the rest of them 73(47.7) on grade 12 Most of them have an excellent health state 113 (73.9) and 31 (20.3) in a good health state.

Pie-chart 1: Nights of interrupted sleep.

More than half, 103(67.3) has interrupted sleep (Insomnia 1-2/Days in a Week and 43(28.1) has interrupted sleep Insomnia 5 to 3/Days in a Week while 6(3.9) has interrupted sleep (Insomnia 6 to 7/Days in a Week. More than half 83 (45.2%) have an excellent school performance and 60 (39.2%) said they have very good performance Minority 10(6.5) answer good More than half 127 (83%) eat 1-3 meals/Day and the rest 26(17) eat more than 3 Only a minority 12 (7.8%) said they suffer gross obesity in contrast of 140 (91.5%) who said they have no obesity. More than half of student (54(35.3) do not nap during classes , 53(34.6) are Rarely While minimum 4(2.6)

Always nap during classes around half of the student 49(32) feeling sleepy sometimes when they doing

homework at evening While 14(9.2) Never feeling sleepy when they doing homework 26(17) Rarely and 28(18.3) Always 35(22.9) Most nights large number of student 125(81.7) do not take anything to get sleep While 2(1.3) always take anything to get sleep 10(6.5) says Sometimes and 3(2) take anything to get sleep most night large number of student 66(43.1) did not loose their interest in hobbies and activities 37(24.2) answer sometimes 25(16.3) for Rarely and the minimum 11(7.2) Most nights the study shows that most of the students 109(71.2%) have factors at home that interrupts their sleep while 42(27.5) answer no 133 (86.9%) of the students complaining of family and social problems while 20(13.1) they don't most of the students 59(38.6) sometimes facing problems in

going to bed 43(28.1) answer for rarely 35(22.9) for Most nights and 2(1.3) for always

Most of the students 49 (32%) saying that they sometimes feel sleepy while doing their homework at evenings, 35 (22.9%) most nights, 28 (18.3%) always, 26 (17%) rarely, 14 (9.2%) never and 1 (0.7%) is missing.

125 (81.7%) answered that they never take anything that helps them to sleep, while 12 (7.8%) answered for rarely, 10 (6.5%) sometimes, 3 (2%) most nights, 2 (1.3%) always and 1 (0.7%) is missing.

Almost half of the students 66 (43.1) answered that they never lose their interests in their usual hobbies and activities, 37 (24.2%) their answer was sometimes, 25 (16.3%) rarely, 12 (7.8%) always, 11(7.2%) most nights and 2 (1.3%) are missing.

48 (31.4%) of the students are saying that they never take caffeine or energy drinks, while 33 (21.6%) answered for sometimes, 30 (19.6%) always, 22(14.4%) rarely and 20 (13.1%) most nights.

Large group of the students 116 (75.8%) do not have any health problems affects their sleep, 19 (12.4%) rarely, 11(7.2%) sometimes, 5 (3.3%) most nights and 2 (1.3%) always 110 (71.9%) of the students always uses internet or electronic games, while 26 (17%) most nights, 11 (7.2) sometimes, 3 (2%) never, 2 (1.3%) rarely and only 1 (0.7%) is missing.

DISCUSSION:

The purpose of the study is to determine the factors of environment and social in relation to insomnia in adolescents. the study provides evidence that there is no relation between insomnia and academic achievements, as the result showed insomnia has no effect on adolescents performance correlated to the study of Hong Kong. Sleep compensation but not naps

may be a protective factor of poor academic performance.

In addition to that, the result showed no relation between insomnia and use of electronics and study conducted in University of Bergen, The results of our study suggest that the use of computers and mobile telephones in the bedroom, may be associated with poor sleep habits among young adults, but not with symptoms of insomnia.

Also, the result showed the insomnia loss linked in body weight and study conducted to University of Chicago. Insomnia is a prevalent health complaint that is often difficult to evaluate reliably, there is evidence that sleep loss is linked to weight gain, in particular abdominal weight gain. Too little sleep has been shown to slow the body's resting metabolism.

Moreover, the result showed there is some factors like family and social increase possibility of insomnia and study conducted to Bernert, Rebecca Family life stress was significantly associated with increased insomnia symptomatology, Results also revealed that negative family life events together with academic stress, predicted the highest levels of insomnia.

This study offers help adolescents determinant increasing factor for insomnia. One of the limitations of this study narrow research periods and small sample used another limitations, is that the methods used to estimate productivity have not been validated.

Recommendations:

- Avoid heavy meals in the evening hours. High-protein meals may keep you awake.
- Try to fall asleep and wake up during the exact time every day (even on weekends) to help your body establish a normal sleep pattern.
- Avoid exposure to bright light before you're going to sleep
- Try to avoid foods and beverages that contain caffeine, such as coffee, tea, chocolate, soft drinks and energy drinks
- Experts recommend aerobic [exercise](#) 3 to 5 times per week as a means of improving the quality and regularity of sleep

CONCLUSION:

The findings indicate that insomnia is a prevalent problem among Saudi female adolescents 15- to 19-years old and more than half of patients in high-school settings have sleep problems Insomnia is a symptom, not a cause. It is the way your body reacts when there is something wrong.

Each insomnia case is different, resulting from different causes. You must determine what is causing insomnia in your particular case.

Depending on the cause of your insomnia, determine what individual treatment options are best for you.

Be persistent in your efforts. It may take several weeks for your body to react to a particular treatment and for results to become evident. Don't be afraid to experiment.

Sleeping pills are only temporary fixes and not the insomnia solution. In fact, they can worsen the problem, create dependency, and cause many unwanted side effects.

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